

Growth of Feminism in Indian English Fiction: Major Nuances

Dr. Nidhi Mishra

Assistant Professor, Department English, Govind Sarang Govt Law College
Place – Bhatapara (CG)

Corresponding author- **Dr. Nidhi Mishra**

Email- redsonja2580@gmail.com

Abstract

Men in India always had a privileged position in Indian society. They are the torch bearers of the patriarchal system existing in Indian society. They have been in an advantageous position in gaining upper hand over women in almost all matters. Broadly speaking there are three phases in the growth of feminism in India, British Period, Freedom Movement and Post Independence. “Real talk “ about Feminism in India can be attributed to the decades of the 1970s. Feminism, female power, women rights and such terms started to have gravity and seriousness of its own. Men started to hear distinct feeble voices of protest and assertion. This led to significant changes in law and regulations. Indian English writers like Kamla Das, Shashi Deshpande, Ruth Jhabwala, Anita Desai, Kamla Markandeya, Shobha De and many more have often explored what it is like to be a woman in Indian society. Even male writers like RK Narayan, Mulk Raj Anand, Salman Rushdie have rejected the male hegemony and have discussed women rights. Indian English writers have done monumental work to vent the voice of downtrodden women in Indian society. Though contributing almost half a population, Indian women have been exploited to the core.

Keywords – Feminism, Woman, Society, Patriarchal

“Remember, all men would be tyrants if they could. If particular care and attention is not paid to the ladies, we are determined to foment a rebellion, and will not hold ourselves bound by any laws in which we have no voice or representation.”

- Abigail Adams, 1776

Introduction

Men in India always had a privileged position in Indian society. They are so called the ‘torch bearers’ of the patriarchal system existing in Indian society. They have been in an advantageous position in gaining upper hand over women in almost all matters. Women are exploited sexually, socially and financially by their male counterparts. Their spirits are crushed to let them become servile and subversive. Feminism in India means providing equal rights to women to their male counterparts. It also means more working opportunities, financial independence, and sexual freedom. It can be summed as rejecting all existing patriarchal notions meant to suppress women.

Growth of Feminism in India

Broadly speaking there are three phases in the growth of feminism in India. The first stage began in the mid-nineteenth century during British rule. With the endless efforts of social reformists like Raja Ram Mohan Roy, Jyotiba Phule, Savitri Phule and many more reforms for women started to trickle down. The precursor was when male European pioneers started to take a stand in opposition to the social shades of malice of Sati (Gangoli, 2007). The second stage can be attributed from 1915 to Indian independence, when our National leader Mahatma Gandhi joined women's developments into his various freedom movements. He ensured that there was equal participation of women in all protests and often urged men to respect women and advocated

for their education. The third stage, post-independence ushered women rights into new momentum. There was a great urgency for equal treatment of women in the work power and right to political equality. The “real talk “ about Feminism in India can be attributed to the decades of the 1970s. Feminism, female power, women rights and such terms started to have gravity and seriousness of its own. Men started to hear distinct feeble voices of protest and assertion. This led to significant changes in law and regulations. Government started to treat its women voters with more dignity and respect. They brought about welcoming changes in policies, rules and regulations. Journalists started covering news on women atrocities and exploitation. Writers in different languages started writing about the predicament of the women. It was in these times that we witnessed the growth of feminism in Indian English Fiction.

Major Feminist Writers in Indian English Fiction

Indian English Writers like Kamla Das investigated the common women's problems and dilemma in everyday life. She often talks about the financial independence of women in their empowerment. Das portrays women trapped in their poverty like Rukmani in Nectar in a Sieve and Nalini in A Handful of Rice, whereas in The Golden Honeycomb she talks about economic freedom. Shashi Deshpande portrays pathetic and suppressive

conditions of women both in home and social life. Deshpande focuses on the growth of woman by recognizing the weakness, overcoming them and asserting one's own identity. Bapsi Sidhwa features financial state of Parsi women. Male writers too are visibly revolted by the atrocities on women and the patriarchal system of hegemony. R.K. Narayan is worried about house-spouses of working class families. While, Mulk Raj Anand exposes the socio-religious unreasonability and shallowness existing in Indian society. Anita Desai dissects the minds and thought process of women who are suffering so much in the hands of their men whether as father, husband or brother. The main female characters in *Cry, the Peacock* and *Voices in the City*, Maya and Monisha finally stand up against the atrocities of their husband and assert their position. Another phenomenal feminist writer is Nayantara Sahgal. Sahgal's protagonists are portrayed as women fighting their male oppressors. In her works like *the Day in Shadow* and *Rice Like Us*, protagonists fight for their equal rights. They finally reject the 'male centric' conception of life and society. Thus, Sahgal in her inimitable way shows "maleness" is not important for a woman's survival. Kamla Markandeya ponders about the dilemma of women and her conflicting east – west experiences. Contemporary writer Salman Rushdie often portrays sexual maltreatment of youngsters in social strata. Writers like Shobha De who herself had unconventional lifestyle shatters the myth of "good woman". De explores sexual independence of women in present days. She also caricatures the hegemony of males in every possible way. De often discusses the life of a modern woman, her ambitions and gratification. In *Socialite Evenings*, the protagonist Karuna has a physical relationship with another man and accepts it freely. Similarly in the *Sisters*, the hero Mallika Hiralal is an ambitious woman who does business on her own terms and neither needs male counsel. Similarly, Feminism in English short stories started with the publication of short stories of self by Kamala Sathianandan in the year 1898. Later on Anita Desai in her phenomenal work "Recreations at Twilight and Different Stories" in 1978 muses over her womanhood, self and impending life. Desai often focuses on the fragile relationship between men and women. She urges women to overcome male suppression and vent their voice. According to Deshpande her protagonists are not mere characters but represent Indian womanhood. Writers like Rajeshwari Sunder Rajan, Leela Kasturi, Sharmila Rege and Vidyut Bhagat are some other group of essayists and critics, who have often depicted rights of women and the notion of feminism in Indian English literature. They have rejected "property status" and

objectification of women exposing the hollowness of the Indian patriarchal system.

Conclusion

Indian English writers have done monumental work to vent the voice of downtrodden women in Indian society. Though contributing almost half a population, Indian women have been exploited to the core. It is these dire conditions which Indian English writers have portrayed in their phenomenal works. They have created awareness and consciousness about the plights of women. To conclude it would be apt to quote Beauvoir, "Representation of the world, like the world itself, is the work of men; they describe it from their own point of view, which they confuse with absolute truth."

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